

The Effect of the Eid Homecoming Prohibition on Migrants as A way To Reduce of Covid 19 in Indonesia

Dr. RINA, S.Pd. S.E., M.M¹, Dr. ANDI HENDRA SYAM., S.E., MS.i², Dr. ANDI NURYADIN., S.E., MS.i³

STIM LPI Makassar, Jl. Bung No.23, Tamalanrea Jaya, Kec. Tamalanrea, Makassar, Sulsei, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The effect of the Eid homecoming ban on migrants as a way to suppress the spread of Covid 19 in Indonesia. The purpose of this study was to determine and analyze the effect of the Eid homecoming prohibition on migrants as a way to suppress the spread of Covid 19 in Indonesia, Larangan Lebaran and have an influence on the number of spread of Covid 19 in Indonesia. The results of the study describe a simultaneous test $Y = - 429 X$ From the above problems, the effect of the Eid homecoming ban is very influential, so the central government and local governments should further increase the Eid homecoming ban for migrants as a way to suppress the spread of Covid 19 in Indonesia.

KEYWORDS: Prohibition of Eid homecoming, How to Suppress the Spread of Covid 19

BACKGROUND

(D Sulistiyono, 2020) As is known by the government through the Covid-19 task force to tighten the rules for long-distance travel, this latest travel regulation will take effect from April 22, 2021 to May 5, 2021 and May 18-24, 2021. Meanwhile, in the period of prohibition of going home for Eid 6-17 may 2021 still apply the old rules. (D Sulistiyono, 2020) this rule is contained in the Circular of the Head of the Covid-19 Handling Task Force number 13 of 2021 concerning the elimination of homecoming in the month of Ramadan and Eid Al-Fitr in 1442 Hijriah during 6-17 May 2021. Previously, the government issued an addendum which regulates addition of travel regulations before and after Eid. This is to prevent the transmission of the corona virus which is spread due to increased community mobility during Eid. This prohibition applies to land, sea and air transportation modes. There are only a few trips permitted by the government with strict conditions. The homecoming prohibition applies to land transportation which is prohibited during homecoming in the form of public motorized vehicles with buses and passenger cars. (D Sulistiyono, 2020) The prohibition also applies to individual or private motorized vehicles, with the types of passenger cars, cars, buses and temporary motorbikes, there are exceptions for people who have urgent interests during Eid including:

1. People who work or go on official trips, such as civil servants, employees of BUMN / BUMD, Polri, TNI, or private employees who are equipped with an assignment letter and signature of the leadership.
2. Visiting sick family.
3. Visits of the deceased's family members
4. Pregnant women with one companion
5. People with the interest of giving birth to a maximum of 2 companions
6. Emergency health services.

Seeing this fact, the title of the writing that we took:

"The Effect of the Lebaran Homecoming Ban on Migrants as a Way of Suppressing the Spread of Covid 19 in Indonesia."

FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM

(Deliarnov, 2003) Based on the background description of the problems above, the problem formulations in this study are as follows:

1. How to ban Lebaran homecoming as a way to suppress the spread of Covid 19 in Indonesia.

RESEARCH PURPOSES

1. Analyze and describe the ban on Eid homecoming as a way to reduce the spread of Covid 19 in Indonesia.

The Effect of the Eid Homecoming Prohibition on Migrants as A way To Reduce of Covid 19 in Indonesia

THEORETICAL REVIEW

1. Prohibition Of Lebaran Hudking

This rule is contained in the Circular of the Head of the Covid-19 Handling Task Force number 13 of 2021 concerning the elimination of homecoming during Ramadan and Idul Fitri 1442 Hijriah during 6-17 May 2021. Previously the government issued an addendum regulating additional travel regulations before and after This is to prevent the transmission of the corona virus which is spread due to increased community mobility during Eid. This prohibition applies to land, sea and air transportation modes. There are only a few trips permitted by the government with strict conditions. The homecoming prohibition applies to land transportation which is prohibited during homecoming in the form of public motorized vehicles with types of buses and passenger cars (D Sulistiyono, 2020) The prohibition also applies to individual or private motorized vehicles, with passenger cars, cars, buses and temporary motorbikes, there are exceptions for people who have urgent interests during Eid include:

1. People who work or go on official trips, such as civil servants, BUMN / BUMD employees, police, military, or private employees who are equipped with an assignment letter and signature of the leadership.
2. Visiting sick family.
3. Visits of the deceased's family members
4. Pregnant women with one companion
5. People with the interest of giving birth to a maximum of 2 emergency health service assistants.

2. How To Press The Spread Of Covid 19 In Indonesia

To prevent a new corona virus cluster, the COVID-19 handling task force asked the public to implement daily protocols. The use of masks and frequent hand washing are the most important things in suppressing this outbreak. Adhering to health protocols is very important, because the cases of the corona-covid 19 virus in Indonesia are still high, new cases. The total number of covid cases stands at 307 thousand.

RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in this research is causal, namely research to determine the effect of one or more independent variables on the dependent variable. In this case, it is knowing the role of the Eid homecoming ban, how to reduce the spread of Covid 19 in Indonesia.

HYPOTHESIS

The research hypothesis is the researcher's assumption of a problem that is being studied. The hypothesis in this study is that it is suspected that there is an effect of the Eid homecoming ban on how to suppress the spread of Covid 19 in Indonesia.

POPULATION AND SAMPLE

The population in this study were 40 honorary lecturers.

The sample used is saturated sampling, so the entire population is sampled in this study.

Variables and their Measurements

Variable	Indicator
Prohibition of Lebaran Homecoming (Variable X1)	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Applies to all.2. No traveling3. Joint Leave4. Provision of Social Assistance5. Religious Activities6. Traffic Control.
How to Suppress the Spread of Covid 19 in Indonesia (Variable Y)	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Wash hands properly.2. Using a mask3. Maintain endurance4. Implement physical distancing and isolation independently.5. Cleaning the house and doing dissection regularly

The Effect of the Eid Homecoming Prohibition on Migrants as A way To Reduce of Covid 19 in Indonesia

The scale used is an ordinal measurement, which is a scale based on ranking and sorted at the higher level to the lowest level or vice versa. Riduan (2004: 82), the answer category consists of 5 levels, namely:

- 5 = Strongly Agree
- 4 = Agree
- 3 = Simply agree
- 2 = Disagree
- 1 = Disagree

VARIABLE OPERATIONAL DEFINITION

1. Eid Homecoming Prohibition

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1. People who work or travel on an official basis, such as civil servants, employees of BUMN / BUMD, Police, TNI, or private employees who are equipped with an assignment letter and signature of the leadership.
2. Visiting sick family.
3. Visits of the deceased's family members
4. Pregnant women with one companion
5. People with the interest of giving birth to a maximum of 2 companions
Emergency health services.

2. How to Press the Spread of Covid 19 in Indonesia

To prevent a new corona virus cluster, the COVID-19 handling task force asked the public to implement daily protocols. The use of masks and frequent hand washing are the most important things in suppressing this outbreak. Adhering to health protocols is very important, because the cases of the corona-covid 19 virus in Indonesia are still high, new cases. The total number of covid cases stands at 307 thousand.

METHOD OF COLLECTING DATA

Field Research

Primary data is data that is collected by individuals or organizations directly through its object (J. Suprpto in research methods book 2001: 5). The research was conducted by distributing questionnaires to all respondents.

Data analysis method

(Ghozali, Application of Multivariate Analysis with SPSS Program., 2005) The data obtained were then analyzed to test the hypothesis using multiple regression analysis techniques. Data processing was performed using SPSS (Statistical Product and Service Solution) version 12.00, with the following analysis procedures:

1. Test Assumptions
2. Multiple Regression Analysis

Testing the hypothesis whether or not there is a significant influence simultaneously between variables.

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2$$

Where Y = Performance Improvement

A = Constant (X = 0)

b₁b₂ = Regression Coefficient

X₁ = Regional Minimum Wage

X₂ = Salary per Teaching Session

X₃ = BPJS

Simultaneous Hypothesis Test

Fcount = R² (N-m-1)

M (1-R²)

The Effect of the Eid Homecoming Prohibition on Migrants as A way To Reduce of Covid 19 in Indonesia

The hypothesis is:

Ho: The Lebaran Homecoming Prohibition does not have a significant effect on how to reduce the spread of covid 19.

Ha: The ban on Eid homecoming has a significant effect on how to reduce the spread of covid 19.

The hypothesis is tested with a confidence level of 95%, so that the α used is 0.05. By using the two-tailed test, then $(n - k; \alpha / 2)$.

So $38 - 2; \alpha = 0.005 / 2 = 0.025$.

Decision-making

Based on probability:

If Probability > 0.05 then Ho is accepted.

If probability < 0.05 then Ho is rejected.

RESULTS ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

(Ghozali, Application of Multivariate Analysis with the SPSS Program. 2005) This chapter discusses the results of the data that the author has collected from as many as 40 travelers. The results of this analysis will be used to see **THE EFFECT OF THE EID HOMECOMING PROHIBITION ON MIGRANTS AS AWAY TO REDUCE OF COVID 19 IN INDONESIA.**

The analysis was carried out as follows:

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	,429 ^a	,184	,163	,06285	,184	8,582	1	38	,006

a. Predictors: (Constant), PROHIBITION OF HOMECOMING IED

a. Predictors: (Constant), X1 (Prohibition of going home)

b. Dependent Variable: Y (Suppressing the Spread of Covid 19).

The regression between the variable prohibition of homecoming and how to suppress Covid 19 in Indonesia can be described in data processing with SPSS software version 22.00 R2 value (coefficient of determination) is 0.429. This shows that the magnitude of the variation that has an effect on the prohibition of wandering homecoming and the spread of Covid19 is 42.9% or the remaining 67.1%.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1,988	,356		5,584	,000
	PROHIBITION OF HOMECOMING IED	,339	,116	,429	2,929	,006

a. Dependent Variable: HOW TO REDUCE THE SPREAD OF COVID 19

Variable Prohibition of Homecoming Against the Spread of Covid 19

Ho = there is no effect of the ban on going home to the spread of covid 19

Ha = there is an effect of the ban on going home to the spread of covid 19

From the calculation, the significance value for the homecoming prohibition variable is $0.006 > 0.005$, so Ha is accepted or Ho is rejected. Thus, it is concluded that the homecoming prohibition variable has a significant effect on the distribution of covid 19

The Effect of the Eid Homecoming Prohibition on Migrants as A way To Reduce of Covid 19 in Indonesia

(Ghozali, Application of Multivariate Analysis with the SPSS Program., 2005). The regression coefficient value is 0,000. This means that with other factors considered constant, the effect of the ban on going home to the spread of Covid 19 is because the result is 0,000. The regression coefficient value on the wage subsidy assistance variable is 0,000. This means that with other factors considered constant, then each Eid homecoming prohibition is (0,000). The regression coefficient value on the variable prohibition of the Lebaran homecoming is 0,000. so any increase in the ban on Eid homecoming will reduce the spread of Covid 19 by 100%.

Beta for X = -429 ... thus the variable of homecoming prohibition has a coeffisein of 0.429. So by referring to the beta results (Unstandardized Coefficients) above, the regression equation can be generated as follows:

$$Y = -429 X1$$

A table showing the relationship between X and Y

Hypothesis Test with Significance Test and F Test

Simultaneous test with the F-test aims to determine the mutual influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	,034	1	,034	8,582	,006 ^b
	Residual	,150	38	,004		
	Total	,184	39			

a. Dependent Variable: HOW TO REDUCE THE SPREAD OF COVID 19

b. Predictors: (Constant), PROHIBITION OF HOMECOMING IED

From the ANOVA test or F-test, it is obtained that F count is 0.184 and with a probability of 8.582. The probability is much greater (>) than 0.05, so the regression model can be used to predict the ban on going home. The SPSS output also shows a p-value of 0.06 > 0.05, which means that it is significant in this case, Ha is accepted or Ho is rejected. Thus it can be concluded that the variable prohibition of going home for Eid has an effect on how to suppress the spread of covid 19 A.

Data Interpretation

Based on the statistical test results, it can be seen clearly that:

The Effect of the Eid Homecoming Prohibition on Migrants as A way To Reduce of Covid 19 in Indonesia

Simultaneously, all independent variables have a significant effect on the dependent variable with the sig value. $0.06 < \alpha < 0.05$. The influence given by the independent variable is positive, meaning that there is a high prohibition on going home, it will result in a higher way of suppressing the spread of covid.

CONCLUSION

From the results and discussion, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Hypothesis test results at a significance level of 0.06, then H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected simultaneously. Thus H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected and variable X has a positive and significant effect on Y.

2. The regression equation formed

$$Y = - 429 X1$$

A positive sign means that if the Eid homecoming ban (X_1) is increased, it can add to suppressing the spread of the Covid 19 (Y) Pandemic.

3. The value of R square or the coefficient of determination which shows the amount of contribution from the influence of X on Y is 42.9% or the remaining 67.1% comes from other factors outside of this study.

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